

Social Stigma and Child Abuse in Uttarakhand: Barriers to Reporting and Recovery

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Rooted in cultural constructs of honor (*izzat*) and collectivistic social frameworks, the social stigma surrounding child sexual abuse (CSA) significantly impacts disclosure, reporting, and recovery processes in India. This study was conducted to examine the operationalization of stigma within child protection responses in Uttarakhand, a largely rural and hilly state, focusing on family reactions, community perceptions, and institutional practices. A qualitative research approach was used to conduct this study. In-depth, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 18 key stakeholders across 11 districts, including Child Welfare Committee (CWC) members and state-level officials. Thematic analysis was done to analyze the data, guided by stigma, labeling, and ecological systems theories. The data analysis revealed that social stigma contributes to underreporting of CSA, shapes family and professional responses, and limits the efficacy of support systems available to survivors.

Keywords: Social stigma, child abuse, Uttarakhand, victim-blaming, parental rejection

In India, collectivist principles have a big impact on social life. Ideas such as *izzat* (honor), social status, and group reputation are crucial for maintaining social order. The term *izzat*, commonly used in Urdu and Punjabi contexts, extends beyond individual dignity to encompass family honour and social validity within the community (Gill, 2014). It signifies respect, moral standing, and social acceptance, serving as a basic principle in various patriarchal and collectivist societies (Dorjee & Ting-Toomey, 2015). In this context, family honour is often perceived as closely tied to the conduct of family members, particularly women and girls, who are often depicted as embodiments of moral purity (Kushal & Manickam, 2014). This cultural logic has important implications for how sensitive issues, including Child Sexual Abuse (CSA), are addressed in a society.

Existing research indicates that honor-based norms influence social behavior by discouraging public acknowledgment of events seen as bringing shame to the family (Gilbert et al., 2004; Thapar-Olmos & Myers, 2018). In cases of CSA, disclosures may be perceived as threatening not only the child's reputation but also the family's overall standing. Families often expect consequences such as social gossip, lowered marriage prospects, exclusion from community or religious activities, and reputational harm, which can lead to silence around abuse (Bhugra, 2002; Reavey et al., 2006). Therefore, fear of social stigma serves as a major obstacle to reporting abuse and seeking help.

The collectivist nature of Indian society further reinforces the view that individual experiences are seen as collective responsibilities (Chadda & Deb, 2013). In this social framework, sexual victimization might be seen not just as personal harm but as a collective dishonor that impacts the family and, sometimes, the larger community. Gendered expectations are central to this process. While honor norms apply to both men and women, they function differently for each gender. Men are often expected to demonstrate strength, protectiveness, and authority, while women's honor is more tied to sexual purity and behavioral restraint (Keni, 2024). These norms can shape family reactions to CSA, especially when the abuse involves adolescent girls.

CSA is globally recognised as a serious violation of children's rights, with long-term psychological, emotional, and social consequences (WHO, 2020). Similarly, in India, CSA encompasses a wide range of abusive behaviours harming a child, often involving perpetrators known to the child, including trusted adults (MWCD, 2007; Deb & Modak, 2010; Charak & Koot, 2014). Despite its prevalence, this issue remains underreported. Studies indicate that fear of blame, shame, disbelief, and family disruption frequently discourage disclosure, especially when abuse occurs within the family (Gupta & Ailawadi, 2005; Choudhury, 2006; Bhattacharya et al., 2019).

Social stigma further shapes survivors' experiences through the influence of community responses and institutional engagement. Survivors also face social distancing and emotional distress. In some cases, fear of collective backlash, including social boycott, discourages families from approaching legal systems (Human Rights Watch, 2013). Similar patterns of institutional silence have been observed internationally, where professionals fail to respond to CSA in the absence of clear disclosure (Child Safeguarding Practice Review Panel, 2024).

To legally respond to CSA, India has established a comprehensive legal and institutional framework, including the Protection of Children from Sexual Offences (POCSO) Act, 2012; the Juvenile Justice (Care & Protection of Children) Act, 2015; CWCs Childline 1098; and various government and non-governmental initiatives. While these mechanisms have strengthened formal responses,

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underreporting remains a persistent concern, suggesting that legal provisions alone may be insufficient in addressing culturally embedded barriers to disclosure and recovery.

To examine these dynamics, this study draws on Stigma Theory (Goffman, 1963), Labeling Theory (Becker, 1963), and Ecological Systems Theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). Together, these frameworks facilitate an investigation of how stigma operates across individual, familial, community, and institutional levels, shaping experiences of disclosure, support, and protection. Stigma and labeling perspectives contribute to how survivors are perceived and treated, while the ecological perspective highlights the interaction between cultural norms, family structures, and child protection systems.

Situated in Uttarakhand, a largely rural and hilly state characterised by close-knit communities, this study explores how social stigma influences CSA reporting and recovery. By examining parental responses, community attitudes, and institutional practices, the research seeks to contribute to a nuanced understanding of the socio-cultural factors that shape child protection outcomes in a society.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the influence of social stigma and family honour on the reporting and recovery of CSA survivors in Uttarakhand.
- To analyse the impact of societal perceptions on CSA survivors' access to justice and support.

Present Study

This study examines the association of social stigma associated with CSA reporting practices and redressal of CSA. Covering eleven of the thirteen districts, it explores how societal perceptions shape both institutional responses and families' willingness to seek support. Uttarakhand's predominantly mountainous terrain presents persistent accessibility challenges, with limited road connectivity leaving many villages isolated and requiring children to travel long distances to attend school (Papola, 2022). Such conditions increase children's exposure to physical risks and unsafe environments (Kansal & Singh, 2022). As highlighted in various research, the state is also highly vulnerable to natural hazards, including earthquakes, floods, landslides, and forest fires, which frequently disrupt schooling and community life (Panday, 2013; Khanduri, 2019; Kumar & Bhattacharya, 2020). Significant disasters, such as the 2013 floods, have had long-term consequences for infrastructure and education, further intensifying children's vulnerability (National Institute of Disaster Management, 2015).

Further, the socio-economic factors also shape children's experiences in the region. Male out-migration from hill districts in search of employment has altered household structures, increasing caregiving and economic responsibilities for women (Mamgai & Reddy, 2017; Sharma, 2019). Limited local employment opportunities and associated social challenges, including substance use among unemployed youth, further contribute to neglectful environments (Mamgai & Reddy, 2017). Similar intersecting challenges have also been recognised at the national level, including in reports by the Ministry of Women and Child Development (MWCD, 2007, 2017).

Method

Participants

This study included eighteen participants, including 11 males and 7

female officers from district and state child protection systems in Uttarakhand, under the Ministry of Women Empowerment and Child Development. The participants included ten CWC members, five ChildLine (1098) coordinators, two state-level ministry officials, and one NGO representative. Purposive sampling was used to include participants directly involved in child protection services, representing eleven of the state's thirteen districts.

Measures

Two semi-structured interview guides were developed for district-level and state-level participants. The interview schedules were formulated by review of relevant literature, consultations with subject experts, and pilot testing, which supported refinement of question relevance. The interview guide for CWC members focused on district-level child protection processes. Key areas included the functioning of child protection services, barriers to reporting and follow-up, and challenges in redressal of child abuse issues.

For state-level officials, a structured interview guide comprising fifteen questions examined child protection policy frameworks, inter-agency coordination, and systemic gaps. Given the limited availability of officials, questions were designed to be concise.

Furthermore, informal interviews were conducted with ChildLine coordinators due to their frontline role in reporting and intervention. These discussions focused on operational challenges, collaboration with statutory bodies, and public awareness regarding child abuse and reporting mechanisms.

Procedure

Data were collected through face-to-face, semi-structured interviews conducted at the offices of both district and state-level officials. Each interview took approximately forty minutes. Most interviews were audio-recorded with participants' consent. In cases where recording was not permitted, detailed field notes were taken.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was done using a thematic analysis process. Transcripts and field notes were repeatedly reviewed to identify patterns related to social stigma, reporting practices, and institutional responses to CSA. Codes were developed inductively and organised into broader themes reflecting individual, familial, community, and systemic dimensions of child protection.

Results and Discussion

Parental Rejection and Victim-Blaming Rooted in Social Stigma

The results demonstrate that the social stigma associated with victims of sexual abuse constitutes a significant barrier to their well-being and recovery. Participants frequently recounted instances in which families refused to take responsibility for their girl child following disclosure of sexual abuse. This refusal manifested either through an unwillingness to allow the child to remain at home or through explicit rejection. A particularly stark example was reported by a CWC member, who recalled parents stating to their daughter, 'हम तेरा बहिष्कार करते हैं' (we reject you). Such responses illustrate how stigma is not only socially imposed but is also actively reproduced within family structures.

A majority of cases involving parental reluctance were reported when the girls had been sexually abused by a friend. This pattern points toward a prevailing stereotype that frames abuse within a moralized lens, where responsibility is subtly shifted onto the victim. This tendency toward victim-blaming obstructs processes of healing and recovery and reinforces silence within families. Similar patterns of familial rejection rooted in perceived shame have been documented in earlier studies (Human Rights Watch, 2013). Research further indicates that parental rejection, particularly during periods of crisis, can have severe and long-term consequences for a child's psychological well-being. Excessive criticism and humiliation have been shown to contribute to the development of a shame-prone emotional style (Reimer, 1996) while maternal rejection has been associated with increased emotional instability (Aspelmeier et al., 2007).

Within this broader pattern, the study also documented contrasting paternal responses, highlighting that familial reactions are not uniform. In one case, the father rejected the child outright following disclosure. In another comparable case, the father initially responded with anger and shame, stating, 'लड़की का बाप पहले तो बहुत गुस्से में था, बोल रहा था कि इसने तो हमारी बदनामी करा दी है, अब लोग क्या-क्या बातें बोल रहे हैं' (The girl's father was initially very angry, saying that she had brought shame to the family and that people were gossiping about them). This response reflects how concerns about social perception and reputation can overshadow the recognition of victimization.

However, over the following days, the father's emotional response shifted. His anger gradually gave way to grief, self-blame, and emotional distress. According to the participant's account, he was observed crying, holding his daughter, and expressing remorse for not being able to protect her when she needed him most. This emotional transition culminated in his decision to take the child back home after she had been placed in a children's home due to lack of familial support. This shift from rejection to acceptance illustrates the internal conflict experienced by caregivers in collectivist contexts, where deeply embedded social norms coexist with parental attachment and responsibility.

In collectivist societies such as India, individual identity is closely intertwined with family and community identity (Chadda & Deb, 2013). As a result, victimization through CSA is rarely seen as individual harm; it disrupts family honor, silencing survivors amid blame (Human Rights Watch, 2013; Chacko et al., 2022). This framing helps explain why the father's initial reaction was directed not toward the perpetrator but toward the child, whom he perceived—albeit indirectly—as the source of reputational harm. Such responses align with patriarchal value systems in which a girl's perceived purity and chastity are closely tied to familial honor (Keni 2024). The father's statement, “अब लोग क्या-क्या बातें बोल रहे हैं” (now people are talking about us), underscores how social judgment can override personal emotions and shape immediate responses. At the same time, the father's eventual remorse and reintegration of his daughter highlight the tension between cultural conditioning and parental instincts. This case further demonstrates that social norms influence not only immediate reactions but also delayed decision-making processes.

Social Stigma and Rural Constraints Leading to Underreporting

Further evidence of deep-rooted stigma emerged when a parent

expressed resentment and shame toward their own child during a conversation with a CWC member. This interaction illustrates the intense pressure experienced by families to conform to societal expectations of honor and to avoid further stigmatization. Such attitudes reveal how deeply ingrained social norms shape family dynamics and influence individual decision-making. The social isolation experienced by child victims of sexual abuse has been widely documented (Finkelhor & Browne, 1985) and stigma associated with sexual abuse further intensifies this isolation (Human Rights Watch, 2013).

In contexts where families are expected to function as primary support systems, rejection can instead result in profound and lasting harm. The fact that CSA is frequently perpetrated by family members (50-70% of cases) further complicates disclosure and heightens victim-blaming (Human Rights Watch, 2013; Tyagi, 2021). Rejection accompanied by criticism and humiliation may contribute to shame-prone emotional patterns (Reimer, 1996) and is associated with severe psychological outcomes, including post-traumatic stress disorder, depression, maladaptive coping strategies, and, in extreme cases, self-harm or suicidal behavior (Kennedy & Prock, 2018).

The findings also reaffirm that social stigma plays a critical role in the underreporting of child abuse cases, particularly in rural areas. This pattern aligns with earlier studies highlighting stigma as a major barrier to disclosure (Behere, 2017). Participants at both district and state levels consistently emphasized that many cases remain unreported due to fear of social repercussions and shame. One participant noted, “ग्रामीण क्षेत्र होने के कारण कई मामले तो वही दबा दिए जाते हैं” (because these are rural areas, many cases are suppressed at the local level).

Uttarakhand's predominantly rural composition intensifies these challenges. According to the 2011 Census, the state consists of 16,826 rural communities, with approximately 81% having populations below 500. In most districts, 75-85% of rural settlements fall within this category. Such demographic patterns reflect the state's geographical constraints and contribute to close-knit social environments where anonymity is limited. Unlike urban contexts, where reporting may occur with some degree of privacy, rural settings are characterized by high visibility and social familiarity (Ruback & Menard, 2001). Lower population density increases the likelihood of individuals being recognized, thereby discouraging disclosure. This lack of anonymity emerges as a critical factor in underreporting, consistent with the findings of Ruback and Menard (2001).

Societal Attitudes and Professional Responses within Child Protection Systems

Within discussions on social and cultural contexts influencing child protection practices, variations were observed in how participants interpreted adolescent behavior, romantic relationships, and experiences of sexual abuse. One Childline coordinator, who was also associated with a non-governmental organization, described an approach that emphasized understanding adolescent romantic relationships through the lens of age-appropriate awareness, boundary-setting, and education, rather than framing such relationships primarily in legal or criminal terms. In contrast, several other participants expressed reservations regarding adolescents' involvement in romantic relationships, particularly below the age of 18, viewing such relationships as socially unacceptable.

Additionally, accounts emerged in which adolescents who had experienced sexual abuse were referred to using labels such as “क्राइम वाले बच्चे” (children involved in crimes). Similar language was also reported in discussions around adolescent elopement. These narratives illustrate how dominant social norms related to sexuality, morality, and age intersect with professional interpretations of adolescent experiences, shaping the language used and the meanings attached to such cases.

An important dimension of these findings relates to the presence of certain assumptions among individuals engaged in child protection work. While such assumptions are often associated with broader societal attitudes, the data suggest that they may also be reflected within professional contexts. This was particularly evident in discussions concerning girls' friendships with boys, where some participants indirectly linked adolescents' social interactions to their experiences of abuse. Comparable patterns have been documented in earlier research, which indicates that older victims of sexual abuse, particularly adolescents, are more frequently attributed a degree of responsibility for their victimization compared to younger children (Rogers & Davies, 2007; Rogers et al., 2007).

Existing literature suggests that such attributions may be associated with perceptions of adolescents as having greater awareness, autonomy, or sexual knowledge, which can influence how credibility and vulnerability are assessed (Davies & Rogers, 2009; Rogers & Davies, 2007). Within this framework, adolescents may be positioned differently from younger children in terms of how their experiences are interpreted and responded to.

These perspectives have implications for how cases involving adolescents are understood and processed within child protection systems. The manner in which professionals conceptualize adolescent behavior and victimization may interact with family and community responses, potentially influencing parental interpretations, levels of support, and decisions following disclosure. Thus, professional responses form part of a broader social environment in which meanings around abuse, responsibility, and protection are constructed.

Conclusion

This study highlights the deep-rooted social stigma surrounding child abuse in Uttarakhand, which continues to obstruct the reporting of abuse, effective case management, and the functioning of child protection systems. Although the Protection of Children from Sexual Offences (POCSO) Act, 2012, has strengthened mandatory reporting and brought many previously hidden cases to light, it has not been able to eliminate the social stigma attached to abuse. Survivors and their families often face rejection, social isolation, and long-lasting emotional distress after disclosure, which discourages reporting and limits access to adequate support services.

The study is limited in scope, as it focuses only on Uttarakhand and includes a relatively small sample size; therefore, the findings cannot be generalized to all socio-cultural contexts across India. However, the findings strongly emphasize the need for targeted interventions. These include community-based awareness and education programs to challenge negative attitudes toward child abuse, as well as the provision of confidential counseling and support services for victims and their families throughout the reporting and recovery process. Such measures can strengthen the child protection framework and contribute to creating a safer and more supportive

environment for children in Uttarakhand.

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